

**The Square Root of Four, the Non-standard Standard;
A Mathematical Thought Experiment**

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Abstract

The purpose of this paper is to experiment with the standard of the simplified form in mathematics, focusing on the square root of four in particular. By asking why simplification conventions exist, we are able to respectfully ignore them and experiment with the number system itself. The results suggest that anything can be represented as the square root of four and thus simplification exists solely for the purposes of letting others read it. Thus, for the purposes of “gatekeeping” and labeling it “self-explanatory” future papers are able to dodge accountability simply because the proof didn’t fit in the margins.

Introduction

Have you ever wanted to make math more convoluted? Do you want to experiment with already-made systems, specifically the simplified form of math, just because you can? Well, look no further; this paper will deal with all of that. Starting with the definition and format for the simplified form, then a new system solely based around the magical number $\sqrt{4}$.

Simplified form

When it comes to the simplified form in mathematics, there are different ideas depending on the specific field; for example, in algebra and arithmetic, it is assumed to simplify like terms; meanwhile, in statistics, it is assumed to compose the data into a readable and useful format. However, as you can see, the examples above have one common idea: simplification. To make it more readable and understandable while keeping the same "meaning."¹

Sometimes this can be contradictory to some ideas used in mathematics, when one would have to expand or conduct an operation on an equation, making it more convoluted and harder to deal with. One should imagine this as untangling a wire. It may be fine when left untouched, but it'll look better after you untangle it.

Here are a few assumed rules when it comes to mathematics, finally written down:

- Prevent operators from remaining: E.g., $2+4$ should just be 6
- Combine like terms: E.g., $2x + 5x$ should be $7x$
- Use an operator² already made for another repeated operator:

$$\text{E.g., } x + x + x = 3x; x(x) = x^2; 1+2+3+4+\dots+n = \sum_{i=1}^n i; 1(2)(3)(\dots)(n) = n!$$

- In some cases it's reasonable to stop at the most "simplified" spot without having an even more convoluted or absurdly high value.

E.g., It makes more sense to say 10^{15} or 1.0×10^{15} than to say 1,000,000,000,000,000

¹ "Meaning," as in the result being equal to the original equation.

² For example 3 and 4, they only apply when the value is too large or a variable like n exists.

The Square Root of Four

Now it's time to deal with the magical number, the square root of four. Let's deal with some basic definitions.³ What is "four"? Simple; it's just $1 + 1 + 1 + 1$ or 4×1 or 2×2 , etc. As you can see, there are many ways to write four. And what is a square root? It's just the number that, when multiplied by itself, is equal to the base, e.g., $\sqrt{16} = 4$ because $4^2 = 16$. With that covered, let's move on to the system solely based on the square root of four.

We now need to represent some basic numbers with the square root of four, to start with the foundations.

Basic integers	Square root of four form/forms	Simplified
0	$\sqrt{4} - \sqrt{4}$	$2 - 2$
1	$\frac{\sqrt{4}}{\sqrt{4}}$	$\frac{2}{2}$
2	$\frac{\sqrt{4}}{\sqrt{4}} + \frac{\sqrt{4}}{\sqrt{4}}$ or $\frac{\sqrt{4}+\sqrt{4}}{\sqrt{4}}$	$\frac{2}{2} + \frac{2}{2}$ or $\frac{2+2}{2}$
3	$\frac{\sqrt{4}+\sqrt{4}+\sqrt{4}}{\sqrt{4}}$	$\frac{2+2+2}{2}$
4	$\frac{\sqrt{4}+\sqrt{4}+\sqrt{4}+\sqrt{4}}{\sqrt{4}}$ or $\sqrt{4} \frac{\sqrt{4}+\sqrt{4}}{\sqrt{4}}$	$\frac{2+2+2+2}{2}$ or $2 \frac{2+2}{2}$
5	$\frac{\sqrt{4}+\sqrt{4}+\sqrt{4}+\sqrt{4}+\sqrt{4}}{\sqrt{4}}$ or $\sqrt{4} \frac{\sqrt{4}+\sqrt{4}}{\sqrt{4}} + \frac{\sqrt{4}}{\sqrt{4}}$	$\frac{2+2+2+2+2}{2}$ or $2 \frac{2+2}{2} + \frac{2}{2}$
6	$\frac{\sqrt{4}+\sqrt{4}+\sqrt{4}+\sqrt{4}+\sqrt{4}+\sqrt{4}}{\sqrt{4}}$ or $\sqrt{4} \frac{\sqrt{4}+\sqrt{4}}{\sqrt{4}} + \frac{\sqrt{4}+\sqrt{4}}{\sqrt{4}}$	$\frac{2+2+2+2+2+2}{2}$ or $2 \frac{2+2}{2} + \frac{2+2}{2}$

³ We will not cover every operator's definition; this is just meant to talk about the square root of four.

As you can see from the table above, there are many ways to represent an integer. Let's try to make one as complex as possible. Assume $x = 2$ and $y = 4$, we can say that $x = \frac{y}{x}$ and we can replace x with $\frac{y}{x}$ to get $x = \frac{y}{\frac{y}{x}}$, we can continue forever with this pattern: $x = \frac{y}{\frac{y}{\frac{y}{\dots}}}$ or $x = y/(y/(y/(y/ \dots)))$. Using this formula we will use the square root of four instead,

$$x = \frac{\sqrt{4} + \sqrt{4}}{\sqrt{4}}, y = \sqrt{4} \frac{\sqrt{4} + \sqrt{4}}{\sqrt{4}} \text{ So we can say that } \frac{\sqrt{4} + \sqrt{4}}{\sqrt{4}} = \frac{\sqrt{4} \frac{\sqrt{4} + \sqrt{4}}{\sqrt{4}}}{\frac{\sqrt{4} \frac{\sqrt{4} + \sqrt{4}}{\sqrt{4}}}{\sqrt{4}}}$$

Integers

A formula to represent positive integers may use a summation $\sum_{i=\frac{\sqrt{4}}{\sqrt{4}}}^n \frac{\sqrt{4}}{\sqrt{4}}$, where n is the

number you want; this is the exact same as just $\frac{n\sqrt{4}}{\sqrt{4}}$, so from $\frac{10\sqrt{4}}{\sqrt{4}}$ or just 10, you get

$\frac{\sqrt{4} + \sqrt{4} + \sqrt{4} + \dots + \sqrt{4}}{\sqrt{4}}$ which can be represented as $\frac{\sum_{i=\frac{\sqrt{4}}{\sqrt{4}}}^n \sqrt{4}}{\sqrt{4}}$ You could be extra fancy and use an integral

as well, $\int \frac{\sqrt{4}}{\sqrt{4}} dn$ to get $\frac{n\sqrt{4}}{\sqrt{4}}$

Decimal Numbers

As long as they remain rational, we can represent them as $\frac{a}{b}$, where a and b are integers.

So 0.5 would look like $\frac{\sqrt{4}}{\sqrt{4} + \sqrt{4}}$, 0.25 would look like $\frac{\sqrt{4}}{\sqrt{4} + \sqrt{4} + \sqrt{4} + \sqrt{4}}$, and 0.333... would be

$$\frac{\sqrt{4}}{\sqrt{4} + \sqrt{4} + \sqrt{4}}, \frac{a}{b} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^a c}{\sum_{i=1}^b c}, \text{ where } c = \sqrt{4}$$

Irrational Numbers

If the irrational number is a physical constraint then keep it as its letter, for example, e , π , and Φ . Otherwise, replace the number in the root with the square root of four forms.

Irrational numbers	Square root of four forms
$\sqrt{2}$	$\sqrt{\frac{\sqrt{4}+\sqrt{4}}{\sqrt{4}}}$
$\sqrt{5}$	$\sqrt{\sqrt{4} \frac{\sqrt{4}+\sqrt{4}}{\sqrt{4}} + \frac{\sqrt{4}}{\sqrt{4}}}$
\sqrt{n}	$\sqrt{\sum_{i=c}^n c}$, where $c = \frac{\sqrt{4}}{\sqrt{4}}$

Imaginary Numbers

We know that $i = \sqrt{-1}$ and so in the form it would be $i = \sqrt{-\frac{\sqrt{4}}{\sqrt{4}}}$

Imaginary numbers	Square root of four forms
$2i$	$\frac{\sqrt{4}+\sqrt{4}}{\sqrt{4}} \sqrt{-\frac{\sqrt{4}}{\sqrt{4}}}$
$3i$	$\frac{\sqrt{4}+\sqrt{4}+\sqrt{4}}{\sqrt{4}} \sqrt{-\frac{\sqrt{4}}{\sqrt{4}}}$
$4i$	$\sqrt{4} \frac{\sqrt{4}+\sqrt{4}}{\sqrt{4}} \sqrt{-\frac{\sqrt{4}}{\sqrt{4}}}$
ni	$(\sum_{i=c}^n c) \sqrt{-c}$, where $c = \frac{\sqrt{4}}{\sqrt{4}}$

Complex Numbers

A combination of a real number and an imaginary number.

General form	Polar form	Exponential form
$a + bi$	$r(\cos\theta + i\sin\theta)$	$re^{i\theta}$
$(\sum_{i=1}^a c) + (\sum_{i=1}^b c)(\sqrt{-c})$	$(\sum_{i=1}^r c) + (\cos(\sum_{i=1}^\theta c) + \sin(\sum_{i=1}^\theta c)\sqrt{-c})$	$(\sum_{i=1}^r c)e^{(\sum_{i=1}^\theta c)\sqrt{-c}}$

Where $c = \frac{\sqrt{4}}{\sqrt{4}}$

Powers of four

Back when we represented the basic integers as $\frac{\sqrt{4}+\sqrt{4}+\sqrt{4}+\dots+\sqrt{4}}{\sqrt{4}}$ or $\sum_{i=1}^n \frac{\sqrt{4}}{\sqrt{4}}$ we also

covered this form $\sqrt{4}^{\frac{\sqrt{4}+\sqrt{4}}{\sqrt{4}}}$, using the exponents instead of addition as the base.

Integers	$\sqrt{4}$ Method (Sum)	$\sqrt{4}$ Method (Exponent)
$4^1 (4)$	$\sum_{i=1}^4 \frac{\sqrt{4}}{\sqrt{4}} = \frac{\sqrt{4}+\sqrt{4}+\sqrt{4}+\sqrt{4}}{\sqrt{4}}$	$\sqrt{4}^{\frac{\sqrt{4}+\sqrt{4}}{\sqrt{4}}}$
$4^2 (16)$	$\sum_{i=1}^{16} \frac{\sqrt{4}}{\sqrt{4}}$	$\sqrt{4}^{\sqrt{4}^{\frac{\sqrt{4}+\sqrt{4}}{\sqrt{4}}}}$
$4^3 (64)$	$\sum_{i=1}^{64} \frac{\sqrt{4}}{\sqrt{4}}$	$\sqrt{4}^{(\sqrt{4}^{\frac{\sqrt{4}+\sqrt{4}}{\sqrt{4}}} + \frac{\sqrt{4}+\sqrt{4}}{\sqrt{4}})}$
$4^4 (256)$	$\sum_{i=1}^{256} \frac{\sqrt{4}}{\sqrt{4}}$	$\sqrt{4}^{(\sqrt{4}^{\frac{\sqrt{4}+\sqrt{4}}{\sqrt{4}}} + \sqrt{4}^{\frac{\sqrt{4}+\sqrt{4}}{\sqrt{4}}})}$

Even Method

We can also use another method, $n = a\sqrt{4} + \frac{\sqrt{4}}{\sqrt{4}}$, where n is an integer and a is half

(rounded down) of n.

Value	$\sqrt{4}$ Method (Even)
3	$\sqrt{4} + \frac{\sqrt{4}}{\sqrt{4}}$
8	$4\sqrt{4} = \sqrt{4} + \sqrt{4} + \sqrt{4} + \sqrt{4}$
1/3	$\frac{\frac{\sqrt{4}}{\sqrt{4}}}{\sqrt{4} + \frac{\sqrt{4}}{\sqrt{4}}} = \frac{\sqrt{4}}{\sqrt{4}} \times \frac{1}{\sqrt{4} + \frac{\sqrt{4}}{\sqrt{4}}} = \frac{\sqrt{4}}{(\sqrt{4})(\sqrt{4}) + \sqrt{4}}$

Examples

Sum Method

$$12 = \sum_{i=1}^{12} \frac{\sqrt{4}}{\sqrt{4}} = \frac{\sqrt{4} + \sqrt{4} + \sqrt{4}}{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$x + 5 = x + \sum_{i=1}^5 \frac{\sqrt{4}}{\sqrt{4}} = x + \frac{\sqrt{4} + \sqrt{4} + \sqrt{4} + \sqrt{4} + \sqrt{4}}{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$0.75 = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^3 \sqrt{4}}{\sum_{i=1}^4 \sqrt{4}} = \frac{\sqrt{4} + \sqrt{4} + \sqrt{4}}{\sqrt{4} + \sqrt{4} + \sqrt{4} + \sqrt{4}}$$

$$\sqrt{2} = \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^2 \frac{\sqrt{4}}{\sqrt{4}}} = \sqrt{\frac{\sqrt{4} + \sqrt{4}}{\sqrt{4}}}$$

$$6i = \left(\sum_{i=1}^6 \frac{\sqrt{4}}{\sqrt{4}}\right) \sqrt{-\frac{\sqrt{4}}{\sqrt{4}}} = \left(\frac{\sqrt{4} + \sqrt{4} + \sqrt{4} + \sqrt{4} + \sqrt{4} + \sqrt{4}}{\sqrt{4}}\right) \sqrt{-\frac{\sqrt{4}}{\sqrt{4}}}$$

$$2 + 3i = \left(\sum_{i=1}^2 \frac{\sqrt{4}}{\sqrt{4}}\right) + \left(\sum_{i=1}^3 \frac{\sqrt{4}}{\sqrt{4}}\right) \sqrt{-\frac{\sqrt{4}}{\sqrt{4}}} = \frac{\sqrt{4} + \sqrt{4}}{\sqrt{4}} + \left(\frac{\sqrt{4} + \sqrt{4} + \sqrt{4}}{\sqrt{4}}\right) \sqrt{-\frac{\sqrt{4}}{\sqrt{4}}}$$

Exponent Method

$$12 = \sqrt{4}^{\sqrt{4}^{\frac{\sqrt{4}+\sqrt{4}}{\sqrt{4}}}} - \sqrt{4}^{\frac{\sqrt{4}+\sqrt{4}}{\sqrt{4}}}$$

$$x + 5 = x + \sqrt{4}^{\frac{\sqrt{4}+\sqrt{4}}{\sqrt{4}}} + \frac{\sqrt{4}}{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$0.75 = \frac{3}{4} = \frac{\sqrt{4}^{\frac{\sqrt{4}+\sqrt{4}}{\sqrt{4}}} - \frac{\sqrt{4}}{\sqrt{4}}}{\sqrt{4}^{\frac{\sqrt{4}+\sqrt{4}}{\sqrt{4}}}}$$

$$\sqrt{2} = \sqrt{\sqrt{4}^{\frac{\sqrt{4}+\sqrt{4}}{\sqrt{4}}} - (\sqrt{4}^{\frac{\sqrt{4}+\sqrt{4}}{\sqrt{4}}} - (\sqrt{4}^{\frac{\sqrt{4}+\sqrt{4}}{\sqrt{4}}} - \dots 2))} = \sqrt{\sqrt{4}^{\frac{\sqrt{4}+\sqrt{4}}{\sqrt{4}}} - \frac{\sqrt{4}+\sqrt{4}}{\sqrt{4}}}$$

$$6i = (\sqrt{4}^{\frac{\sqrt{4}+\sqrt{4}}{\sqrt{4}}} + \frac{\sqrt{4}+\sqrt{4}}{\sqrt{4}})\sqrt{-\frac{\sqrt{4}}{\sqrt{4}}}$$

$$2 + 3i = (\sqrt{4}^{\frac{\sqrt{4}+\sqrt{4}}{\sqrt{4}}} - \frac{\sqrt{4}+\sqrt{4}}{\sqrt{4}}) + (\sqrt{4}^{\frac{\sqrt{4}+\sqrt{4}}{\sqrt{4}}} - \frac{\sqrt{4}}{\sqrt{4}})\sqrt{-\frac{\sqrt{4}}{\sqrt{4}}}$$

Even Method

$$12 = 6\sqrt{4} = \sqrt{4} + \sqrt{4} + \sqrt{4} + \sqrt{4} + \sqrt{4} + \sqrt{4}$$

$$x + 5 = x + 2\sqrt{4} + \frac{\sqrt{4}}{\sqrt{4}} = x + \sqrt{4} + \sqrt{4} + \frac{\sqrt{4}}{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$0.75 = \frac{3}{4} = \frac{\sqrt{4} + \frac{\sqrt{4}}{\sqrt{4}}}{2\sqrt{4}} = \frac{\sqrt{4}}{2\sqrt{4}} + \frac{\frac{\sqrt{4}}{\sqrt{4}}}{(2\sqrt{4}) \times \sqrt{4}} = \frac{\sqrt{4}}{\sqrt{4} + \sqrt{4}} + \frac{\sqrt{4}}{(\sqrt{4} + \sqrt{4})\sqrt{4}}$$

$$\sqrt{2} = \sqrt{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$6i = 3\sqrt{4}\sqrt{-\frac{\sqrt{4}}{\sqrt{4}}} = (\sqrt{4} + \sqrt{4} + \sqrt{4})\sqrt{-\frac{\sqrt{4}}{\sqrt{4}}}$$

$$2 + 3i = \sqrt{4} + (\sqrt{4} + \frac{\sqrt{4}}{\sqrt{4}})\sqrt{-\frac{\sqrt{4}}{\sqrt{4}}}$$

Conclusion

There are many ways to represent numbers, especially with the square root of four discussed in this paper. We conclude that it's entirely possible to simply make any equation much worse for anyone else who comes across it. Does this thought experiment have any real applications? Absolutely, it's to open the fact that anyone can write "bad math" that looks like too much for their peers to handle and really does let it be "an exercise to the reader".